

***In vitro* sensitivity test of ayurvedic formulations against growth of *Rhizoctonia solani* causing sheath blight of Rice in Manipur**

***Kota Chakrapani, Bireswar Sinha, Tokmem Siram, W. Tampakleima Chanu, Tusi Chakma, Bijeeta Thangjam**

Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Central Agricultural University, Imphal, Manipur, India

*Corresponding email: kotachakrapani2@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Short Communication Short Communication Received on Jan 17, 2020 Revised on Feb 20, 2020 Accepted on March 01, 2020 Published on March 10, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Kota Chakrapani, Bireswar Sinha, Tokmem Siram, W. Tampakleima Chanu, Tusi Chakma, Bijeeta Thangjam</p> <p>Corresponding Author Email kotachakrapani2@gmail.com</p>	<p>The antifungal potentialities of three ayurvedic formulations <i>viz.</i>, Bacteridote, fungidote, viridote were evaluated <i>in vitro</i> against <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> causing sheath blight of rice. The current study of antifungal activity was assessed by food poison technique. Different concentrations of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 and 0.4% were evaluated by food poison technique. The results revealed that fungidote showed highest mycelial inhibition followed by viridote and bacteridote. Fungidote and viridote showed cent per cent inhibition at 0.2 and 0.3% concentrations respectively. All ayurvedic formulations considerably inhibited the growth of <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> pathogen. The outcomes direct that the extent of inhibition by all three ayurvedic formulations provides use of excellent potential antagonists capable of reducing the growth of <i>R. solani</i> on sheath blight of rice.</p>
<p>PUBLICATION INFO International Journal of Agricultural Invention (IJAI) RNI: UPENG/2016/70091 ISSN: 2456-1797 (P) Vol.: 5, Issue: 1, Pages: 72-74 Journal Homepage URL http://agriinventionjournal.com/ DOI: 10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.10</p>	<p>KEYWORDS Sheath Blight, Rice, <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>, Ayurvedic Formulations, Food Poison, Mycelial Inhibition</p>

HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Chakrapani, K., Sinha, B., Siram, T., Chanu, W. T., Chakma, T., Thangjam, B. (2020) *In vitro* sensitivity test of ayurvedic formulations against growth of *Rhizoctonia solani* causing sheath blight of Rice in Manipur, *International Journal of Agricultural Invention*, 5(1): 72-74. DOI: [10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.10](https://doi.org/10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.10)

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is the India's pre-eminent cereal crop. Most of the world's human population consumes rice as staple food, especially Asia. Moreover, India is one of the leading producers of the crop. On 27 February 2018, the Government of India stated the production of rice during the 2017 season, pegging total Indian output at an all-time high of 166.5 million tonnes (111.0 million tonnes, milled basis). This level would stand 1.2 percent above the final estimate for the 2016 season (FAO, 2018). In addition to this India is forecast to rise by an additional 1.8 percent in 2018,

to reach an all-time high of 169.5 million tonnes (113.0 million tonnes, milled basis). Being most widely cultivated crop around the country and world, many fungal pathogens show their aggressiveness in attempt to inflict various diseases to the crop. Among them Sheath Blight, a soil borne disease caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* (Kuhn) stands at peak to incur most economically significant losses. Management of sheath blight disease is difficult because the pathogen produces *sclerotia* which remain viable for long time.

Synthetic formulations used for the management practice show drastic effects *i.e.* development of resistance in pathogen, residual toxicity, environmental pollution, high cost and results in more carcinogenic risk than other pesticides which might give rise to avert biological effects on humans and animals etc. (Brent and Hollomon, 1998, Schillberg *et al.*, 2001). Organic farming and bio pesticides, ayurvedic formulations etc., are gaining more importance due to inherent hazardous ramifications involved by the use of formulations in management. The metabolites and secondary metabolites released by some useful microorganisms have some positive inhibitory effect on other disease causing pathogens. By following such sustainable methods to manage or control the disease and disease causing organisms in absence of resistant/ tolerant varieties results in eco of the friendly environment.

Materials and Methods

Isolation of Fungus

The plant showing typical symptoms of sheath blight were collected and were examined under microscope. Later the infected samples were lacerated to small pieces (about 0.5 to 1.0 cm) and were rinsed under running tap water twice. Surface sterilization was done by dipping the pieces in 1% Sodium hypo chloride solution and through a series of sterile distilled water at 3 intervals one minute each respectively. The pieces were dried using a blotting paper. Finally the pieces were then aseptically placed on sterilized potato dextrose agar (PDA) petridishes using sterile forceps. The inoculated petridishes were then incubated in BOD incubator at $25 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$ for two days and observed for growth of the fungus. Purified cultures of the fungus were obtained from hyphal tip culture methods. Identified was done according to the key of Kubick and Harman (1998).

In Vitro Evaluation of Antagonistic Potential of Ayurvedic against Growth *Rhizoctonia solani*

Seven days cultured old isolate of *Rhizoctonia solani* was used for the assessment of ayurvedic formulations. Antagonistic potentials of ayurvedic formulations were assessed by food poison technique. Conical flasks containing 100 ml of PDA were melted and were added with ayurvedic

formulations of desired formulations and poured into petri plates under sterile conditions. The plates without formulations served as control. The plates were then inoculated with *R. solani* culture.

The treated plates were incubated in BOD at $25 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$ for 2 days. The linear growth of mycelia was measured and the recordings were noted. Three replications of each treatment were maintained and the plates without phyto-extracts served as control. The observations on radial mycelial growth were recorded. Mycelial growth was measured at 24 hours interval till the colony in the control plate was covered with the growth of mycelium of pathogen. The Per cent Growth Inhibition (PGI) was calculated by using the formula suggested by Vincent (1947).

$$\text{PGI} = \frac{\text{DC} - \text{DT}}{\text{DC}} \times 100$$

Where,

PGI = Per cent growth inhibition

DC = Average diameter of mycelial colony of control plate

DT = Average diameter of mycelial colony of treated plate.

Table1. List of ayurvedic formulations used against *R. solani* and their concentrations

S. N.	Ayurvedic Chemical	Concentration (%)			
1.	Viridote	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4
2.	Fungidote	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4
3.	Bacteridote	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4

Results and Discussion

The current *in-vitro* studies of ayurvedic formulations on mycelial growth of *R.solani* revealed that all the treatments used deliberately showed a significant control on mycelial growth. All the results obtained are relayed in table 2 and figure 1. Among all treatments tested, fungidote had shown highest percent of inhibition. It has shown cent per cent of mycelial inhibition at 0.2% concentration. The mycelial growth inhibition was next followed by viridote with cent per cent of inhibition at 0.3% of concentration. Bacteridote had shown least mycelial growth inhibition.

The present study concludes that out of three ayurvedic formulations tested by food poison technique for their inhibitory effect, against mycelial growth of *R. solani* at 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 and 0.4% per cent concentration.

Keeping the base of mycelial inhibition it is evident that the treatments of all the ayurvedic formulations used have some toxic principles which directly show their impact on growth of the pathogen.

Table 2. List of ayurvedic formulations and their Inhibition percentage

S. N.	Formulation	Inhibition (%)*
		33.14 (5.80)**
1.	Viridote	68.51(8.31) 100(10.02) 100 (10.02) 65.18 (8.10)
2.	Fungidote	100 (10.02) 100 (10.02) 100 (10.02) 0.37 (0.89)
3.	Bacteridote	9.62 (3.18) 14.07 (3.82) 22.22 (4.77)
SE (d)		0.09
CD(P=0.05)		0.18

Conclusion

It is evident that all ayurvedic formulations used in this investigation exhibited antifungal properties in suppressing the mycelial growth of *R. solani*. These findings showed that for management of *R. solani*, ayurvedic formulations can be used. Hence, further investigation with these potential ayurvedic formulations effective against *R. solani* can be exploited for future plant disease management to control sheath blight of rice with proper field studies.

References

Brent, K. J., Hollomon, D. W. (1998) Fungicide resistance: the assessment of risk. FRAC, Global Crop Protection Federation, Brussels, pp: 48.
 FAO (2018) Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, FAO rice market monitor, **21**: 1.

Fig 1. Effect of ayurvedic formulations on growth of *R. solani*

Kubicek, C. P., Harman, G. E. (1998) *Trichoderma* and *Gliocladium*, Taylor and Francis Ltd, 1 Gunpowder Square, London, EC4A 3DE, **3**: 30.

Schillberg, S., Zimmermann, S., Zhang, M. Y., Fischer, R. (2001) Antibody-based resistance to Plant pathogens, *Trans. Res.*, **10**: 1-12.

Vincent, J. M. (1927) Distortion of fungal hyphae in presence of certain inhibitors, *Nature*, **159**: 850.